

8T – Fermionic and Multiverse Superposition's

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will present the features of linearity concerning Fermions and concerning the universe packet representation. That is that a combinations of certain terms of the same class is also considered a solution, similar to linear differential equations, which takes part in Quantum Mechanical setting.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \tag{1.47}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \tag{1.48}$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \tag{1.49}$$

Now given the fundamentals, it is possible to analyze the subject of linearity for Fermions. Suppose that in two distinct locations arbitrary variations are vanishing into matter. Both have an even amount of arbitrary variations. The combination of the two is also a solution, which keeps the manifold stationary, as it yields an even number that vanishes into matter. That is similar to the superposition of states, the idea of a linear differential equation, which serve a crucial role in Quantum mechanics. The following can be put mathematically:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_1} \delta g_i + \sum_{i=1}^{N_2} \delta g_i = 0$$

$$N_1 \neq N_2$$

$$2 |N_1 \cap N_2$$

That is both are divisors of two, i.e. even number of arbitrary variations. than the described outcome is the summation of the two to be an even number which keeps the manifold stationary, i.e. no curvature is allowed:

$$(N_1 + N_2) = N_{1+2}$$

$$2 |N_{1+2} \rightarrow 0$$

The idea of linearity can be expressed in another manner, that is by pair of two distinct manifolds flattening each other, combined with another pair of two distinct manifold is also a solution of (1.2.A) and how the packet is constructed.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_2} = \mathfrak{Z}_1 = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_3} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_4} = \mathfrak{Z}_2 = 0$$

$$\mathfrak{Z}_1 + \mathfrak{Z}_2 = \mathfrak{Z}_{1+2} = 0$$

Which means that in the universe packet any even number of universe pairs with opposite curvature orientation is a valid solution. The even number can be of any magnitude, and be a result of lower magnitude solutions, which represent pairs of universes flattening each other via areas of extremum curvature, causing outward acceleration from those areas. The superposition concerning Bosons was analyzed in detail in previous papers and for the superposition to hold under addition operation, odd number of primes are required.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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